

Critical Interview Sales Data For Furniture Industry: Sales People Perspective

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 22, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: August 23, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Sales data, Furniture industry, Thailand</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7017130</p>	<p><i>This study aims to identify critical sales data for furniture products from perspective of salespeople in Bangkok Metropolis – capital of Thailand. The qualitative analysis and semi-structured interview were selected as the research method for this study. After relevant literature review, a set of questions about sales data created and later a face to face and online semi-structured interview were conducted to twelve salespeople, including eleven sales staff and one sales manager who are currently working in a furniture company in Bangkok Metropolis in order to identify the critical sales data that contribute to success of a sales team. These critical sales data's storage, analysis, management tools, application and other relevant issues discussed in the interview process were also mentioned in the paper. The interview to eleven sales staff conducted by online format through Google Forms and through sales manager interview used face-to-face semi-structured interview research method. An extensive literature review has identified extant knowledge, theories and methodologies adopted by prior researchers to gain greater understanding of sales data.</i></p>

Introduction

Data was viewed as the precious oil since the end of the 90's. With the development of digital technologies, there is no doubt that the world we live in is surrounded by various data and Covid-19 has accelerated this digital trend. These data were viewed as assets which is one of the most important raw materials in the information age nowadays (Perrons & Jensen, 2015). New technologies, such as cloud service, big data, machine learning, and cognitive computing completely change the way business storage and analyze the data. Furthermore, have a significant impact on decision making process for data-driving products and services. It is because data can be turned into information, information can be refined into knowledge and, finally, knowledge can lead to competent decisions (Jesse, 2021). More than ever, the ability to manage torrents of data is critical to an organization's success (DalleMule& Davenport, 2017). Insufficient data competence is one of the reasons that lead to organization's failure in the innovative industry upgrading process. Many prior researchers have suggested that sales data can help organization make better decision and increase its profit ability when it was correctly identified, storage, analyzed and managed (Neilson, Martin & Powers, 2008). That makes sales data becomes one of the most important data for organizations nowadays. However, capital and resources in an organization is limited that makes it is almost impossible to tracking, storage and manage all sales data. Therefore, identifying the key critical sales data becomes extremely important for an organization.

In sales field, people face the same situation, where key sales data can go a long way in improving sales performance and helping create to successful business. However, in the literature viewed, researchers found only a few papers identifying the key sales data which benefit to furniture products enterprises in Bangkok Metropolis. So, this study aims to learn the sales data that are important for shaping successful sales team, their storage, analysis, application and the way to manage these sales data in business from a perspective of salespeople from a furniture organization in capital of Bangkok, Thailand.

Literature review

As a sales leader, having an in-depth understanding of sales data and set up appropriate sales data strategy is critical in today's digital times. Tracking too few or too much sales data is both viewed as unsuccessful strategy, a successful sales leader needs to find the balance point to use sales data and analyze it effectively (Shawn, 2019).

Sales Data and Sales Metrics

There is no standard definition for sales data among scholars now, however, some concepts can be found in previous research. Emily (2019) argued that sales data is any information that is machine-readable and of benefit to sales teams. Allie (2021) suggested that sales data is, essentially, anything that you can measure in the sales process.

A good sales leader needs to identify the best sales data to track on it because it helps with understanding customers, improving sales team's performance, making better decisions and finally benefit to the whole organization. Furthermore, it will not only offer direct insight into your sales teams, but will also provide market trends and the overall ability to grow your products or services. In short, sales leaders must determine the appropriate sales data, which may differ depending on the organization type, product or service attributes, distribution channel, customer features and other factors. Knowing how to interpret the collected sales data and use its insights to improve enterprises' sales strategy is important in today's business world (Waters, 2011).

Before the sales data can be analyzed, sales leader first needs to understand what the organization is looking for and the reason to looking for it then decide the goal and the main sales data that organization want to track on it. According to research results of some prior scholars, the following sales metrics will provide sales leader with the most valuable information to form the basis of a powerful sales analytics program: 1) Sales Growth 2) Sales Target 3) Sales Funnel 4) Pipeline Velocity 5) Average Contract Value 6) Product Performance 7) Real-Time Competitive and Market Data 8) Selling Time 9) Team Performance.

It's hard to think of any approach to sales analytics that doesn't take sales growth as its foundational metric. Analyzing sales growth involves measuring revenue increase over a fixed period of time. Sales growth is displayed in a percentage and it can be measured by using current month's total sales minus previous month's total sales and divided by previous month's total sales (Shawn, 2019).

The marketing function and sales support departments assist with sales activities and they are all focused on meeting sales targets. Thus, sales targets should be second on your list. Targets help determine your company's growth and form the basis of your company's revenue. Well-defined sales targets unify each level of your company, from executive to salesperson, behind a clearly understood objective. It is fundamental to a consistently successful sales approach. Targets that are too far in the future can be as bad for motivation as targets that are unrealistically hard or easy (Le Meunier-FitzHugh & Piercy, 2010).

The sales funnel is of great importance, and sales leader should assess the nature of the rigorously to determine where the weak points are in the sales strategy. Each stage of the buyer's journey has a different dynamic, so measure sales team's success at each one. The sales leader will almost always find progressively fewer prospects at each stage and they need to define which stage the sales team are loss customer and then make a correct action accordingly (Sergeev, Barykin, Ostrovskaya & Yadykin, 2021).

Measuring pipeline velocity (PV) is a sure way to bring targeted improvements to the organization's sales process. The calculation of PV will tell sales leader how much money coming through your business per sales cycle length. Pipeline velocity equal to qualified opportunities time win rate time deal size and divided by length of sales cycle. Observe the rate of change, not only of the PV but of the metrics that compose it. An understanding of where opportunities were lost will show you how to improve your win rate. Opportunities can be lost due to reasons such as poor pricing, timing of approach, poor targeting, poor pacing and lowered demand (Scherer, 2021).

Increasing average contract value (ACV) is viewed as a powerful driver of exponential growth. Keeping track of an organization's ACV is a vital sales analytics consideration. Measuring and improving your ACV allows sales team to build revenue without having to constantly exceed the month-on-month customer growth numbers. It's actually both easier and cheaper to sell to existing customers than to new ones. Some of the fastest-growing companies prioritize upselling in order to increase ACV and drive revenue (Pustišek & Karasz, 2017).

Organizations rely on their current and new product offerings to meet sales and profit objectives that lead to product performance becomes an important sales metric. If your product is underperforming, even the best sales analytics program in the world will be useless. Product performance can generally be measured in terms of the revenue the products is bringing in and the volume of orders the organization are receiving and fulfilling. The following three contextual cues are particularly valuable to track: Buyer personas are perhaps the most important piece of context to consider when trying to improve product performance. Analyzing Competitors is another key piece of contextual information for the evaluation of product performance. Assess approach to customer relationships and how it might be affecting your product performance. Understanding customer's relationship with organization's product is key to improving the relationship with them. If necessary, try to encourage customers providing constructive critical feedback about organization's products (Langerak, Hultink & Robben, 2004).

A successful sales manager must pay attention to not only the organization's internal sales data, but also to external real-time market competition and other market data related to it, in order to keep abreast of market dynamics and know organization's position that it currently occupies. Based on this real-time competitive and market data, the sales manager can make timely adjustments to the company's sales strategy, ensuring that the company maintains its strategic advantage in a highly competitive market (Weiss & Verma, 2002).

Maximizing sales team's selling time, and optimizing their use of it, is the most decisive factor in the immediate improvement to sales team's performance. Observe sales team's workload and account for the proportion of their hours that are devoted to selling time. Ensure that sell-time logs are implemented and outcomes tracked. Too much time spent on a single stage in a deal or repeated time spent on a potential deal leading to a closed

opportunity can be red flags that stand for customer targeting is flawed. Pre-sale actions like information gathering have been shown to take up significant portions of a sales team's time. A well-integrated CRM at the base of technology stack can make looking for key customer information. As part of your the enablement strategy, implement tools that allow salespeople to outsource or automate non-selling tasks where possible to allow sales team to make the most of their selling time (Rapp, Petersen, Hughes & Ogilvie, 2020).

A key aspect of sales data analysis is looking closely at your sales team to make those important internal calls. Sales enablement, and particularly training, is a process that should never stop in order to improve your sales team's performance by offer them right coaching. This process is to identify sales people who are performing particularly well, while some other sales people maybe need to improve. A good sales manager should clearly know that where your team are struggling and provide necessary training and coaching on them accordingly (Ferreira, 2017).

Besides above sales metrics, below metrics are also important for sales managers to closely track on it. 1) Sales revenue (Huang, Marquardt & Zhang, 2015). This is amount of revenue made from sales over a period of time. It shows an organization's profit margin and sales team's performance as well. Sales revenue equal to total revenue from all sales over a set period of time. 2) Sales forecast accuracy (Rezazadeh, 2020). A sales forecast is never going to be 100% accurate, the closer the better, so it's important to compare your results to what your predicted 3) Ratio of sales made to new vs. existing customers (Stewart,1996). Whether new leads or existing customers are making up the bulk of your sales. It is equal to total revenue for new customers vs total revenue for existing customers. 4) Leads response time (Sabnis, Chatterjee, Grewal & Lilien, 2013). It stands for how long your sales representatives take to respond to new leads in your pipeline which is equal to average of time taken respond to leads 5) Follow up time (Smith, Gopalakrishna& Chatterjee, 2006). It explains how persistent sales representatives are in following up on communications with leads. It is average of time taken before a follow-up communication is made. 6) Leads generated. Lead generation is the beginning of consumer interest or enquiry into a company's products or services. Or it can be defined as a process of attracting prospects and converting them into people interested in your company's products and services. A lead is a customer's contact and, in some situations, demographic information who is interested in a specific product or service. A good sales manager should be aware of your sales team meet their quotas of adding leads to the sales pipeline or not (Erschik, 1989).

Data was once critical to only a few back-office processes, such as payroll and accounting. Today it is central to any business, and the importance of managing it strategically is only growing. There is no avoiding the implications: Organizations that have not yet built a data strategy and a strong data-management function need to catch up very fast or start planning for their exit. For B2C business, organizations like Google, Facebook and Amazon demonstrate the importance of data and how it can result in unprecedented success. The situation for B2B world, organizations strive for a vertical and horizontal integration with their supplies and buyers. There is no doubt that successful organizations approach data management from a strategic perspective. Only when they place data competence at the center of their business, can they make solid decisions based on exploratory analysis, self-service processes, or intelligent algorithm (Jesse, 2021). Some prior researchers have indicated that sales data can help sales leaders make better decisions by identifying ideal customers & enabling effective prospecting, optimizing the sales process, providing sales forecasts, tracking performance against key objectives and supporting ongoing decision-making.

An organization's ideal customer is the company or individual most likely to want to buy your products or services. They're also the most likely to remain loyal and recommend you to others. Sales leaders need data to determine who this target is. This data must include, as a minimum, the names of individuals, the names of their organizations, job titles, email addresses and direct dial phone numbers. Quality sales data will help your sales representative with prospecting for new customers. Additionally, it allows them to identify which prospects are ready for an upsell or a cross-sell pitch, and which prospects are ready to nurture (Zoltners, Sinha & Lorimer, 2012).

Every sales leader wants to improve the way their team works. To do this, a good sales leader need to gain insights. It's incredibly important that your sales team tracks and measures data, preferably on a weekly basis, in order to fine-tune the sales process and win long-term customers. Consistent data tracking can help sales leader pinpoint the bottlenecks in the pipeline (Toman, Adamson & Gomez, 2017).

Sales forecasting empowers sales leader to identify potential issues or risks and then implement appropriate corrective actions to mitigate them. High-quality data will make the forecasting stronger. The sales data you want to use here is income-age geographical distribution, industry news and press releases, macro-economic factors and sector indexes (Lu, 2014).

Sales metrics are data points that represent the performance of team, organization, or individual employees. Tracking the right sales metrics and measuring these against your key objectives will allow management and team to evaluate how they are performing. Then introducing new processes to boost performance (Ittner&Larcker, 2005).

Sales data must be consistent and continually updated to support decision-making. Up-to-date data predicts future trends, drives the creation of new business opportunities, optimizes operational effort and ultimately leads to the generation of new business revenue. Most importantly, implementing a data-driven sales approach should develop, influence, and empower your sales team (Min, 2013).

Source and tools of sales data

A data-driven sales team is capable of producing astonishing results for organizations. But they are only as good as the data they use. Below are two sources of sales data coming from: 1) Public sources. Public sources refer to any data freely available and in the public domain. They include social media profiles, websites and online articles such as blogs or press releases. Another public source is consented-in data is any data that is freely supplied by prospects or customers. 2) Private sources. Private sources of sales data are secured from public view and must be accessed via a subscription or a form of payment or permission. They include data as a service provider, paywalled websites, financial or market intelligence platforms or data collected by organizations its own (Emily, 2019).

It is becoming clear that the generation of data is not the main problem, every online purchase, every product information downloads and every product-related comment on social media generates a wealth of new data. The challenge is not this deluge of data perse so much as the task of integrating it methodically into the IT systems and processing it with suitable tools. The right sales analytics tools will help sales leader get the very best out of both the sales data itself and sales team's time. These suitable tools can analyze sales data, uncover key insights and trends, track progress on deals, measure team performance, improve sales forecasting, and much more. Only once all this data is structured and cleansed can it be used as a reliable basis for business-critical decisions (Jesse, 2021). The following are two main tools to manage and analyze the sales data:

A spreadsheet can help you collate your data, sales-related or otherwise, but a CRM platform with strong insights features is the best option. There are several benefits to using spreadsheets to gather data such as they're free (Google Sheets and Open Office), they provide a helpful real-time overview of your current sales operation and they can be programmed to automatically perform calculations on figures you input. They also have some disadvantage, for example, all data needs to be input manually (Borthick, Schneider & Viscelli, 2017). If a sales leader rather the team spent less time on data entry and more time prioritizing their best leads, then consider moving to a CRM with automated data collating.

The CRM software presents a substantial step up over spreadsheet software in a number of ways. It automatically records interactions with leads in sales pipeline, saving team time otherwise wasted on data entry and helping to make sure never lose track of communications with direct leads. Plus, with mobile app features and third-party integrations, CRMs expand the scope of what you can measure. In sales, many tasks are now managed through centralized cloud software, including CRMs, email marketing platforms and integration tools, making sales data readily available (Girchenko, Ovsianikova&Girchenko, 2017).

Interview findings

Following an online survey through Google form with 11 sales people from a furniture company in Bangkok, as well as a face-to-face semi-structured interview with their sales manager, some interview findings can be concluded as follows:

1) Internal opinion and fact

From the perspective of 11 sales staff. Only a few sales data in this survey are considered unimportant by a tiny proportion of salespeople, as seen in the table below:

Respondents	Sales growth	Sales target	Average contract value	Product performance	Real-time competition and market data	Selling time	Team performance	Sales avenue	Sales forecast accuracy	Ratio of sales made to new VS existing customers	Lead response time	Follow up time	Lead generated	Relationship with customer	Other internal opinion from sales staff
A	5	5	5	5	5	3	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	N/A
B	1	5	4	4	4	3	4	5	4	5	5	4	4	4	All depend on product and competition.
C	4	5	4	5	3	4	4	5	3	3	5	4	4	3	All sales data in this survey is important to reach maximum
D	4	5	4	5	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	4	N/A
E	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	Follow up with customer is important.
F	5	5	4.5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4.5	5	N/A
G	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	Product quality, after-sales service and customer follow up are three most import issues.
H	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	All sales data in this survey is important.
I	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	N/A
J	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	3.5	3	5	4	3.5	All sales data in this survey is important.
K	5	5	4	5	5	3	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	Understand customer's needs is important.

Remark: 5 = Very important, 4 = Important, 3 = Neutral, 2 = unimportant, 1 = very unimportant

From the overview, most of sales staff believed that sales data prevailed is quite important on this survey. Besides this, they proposed that other data such as follow up with customer closely, product quality, customer service after sales and understand customer’s needs are also critical sales data in furniture company should pay much attention on it.

2) From the viewpoint of sales manager, a furniture company who are responsible all sales related matters such as sales avenue, forecasting, select products for promotion and campaigns, communication with customers, team management and other sales activities for the entire Thailand market. He believes that all sales data in the interview is important and rating them from score 4 (important) to 5 (very important) and no sales data was viewed as unimportant data in this manager’s opinion. Among all sales data, sales growth is considered as the most important sales data with full score 5 points, while another nine data factors are given 4 scores as important data such as sales target, product performance, real-time competition and market date, team performance, sales avenue, sales forecast accuracy, follow up time, leads generated and relationship with customer. Four data factors are given 3 points as neutral, they are average contract value, selling time, ratio of sales made to new vs. existing customers and lead response time. In addition to the above sales data, manager of sales department believe that merchandise analysis is another critical data that should be analyzed and tracked closely.

3) Compare the average importance of sales data between sales staff and manager. From the sales people’s average importance perspective, there are 3 most important data - sales target, product performance and sales revenue. It can be explained by below chart when compare the importance of different sales data between sales staff and sales manager.

VS

Above charts show that sales growth viewed as the most important sales data in opinion of sales manager while it is not considered as the three most important data according to survey to 11 sales people. In sales staff opinion, sales target, product performance and sales revenue are regarded as the most important 3 data that should be closely track and deep analyze on it. These 3 sales data were also viewed as important by manager's consideration.

Between sales people and manager, there is a consistent opinion on what data might be considered not so important, they are average contract value, selling time, forecast accuracy, and sales made to new vs. existing customers. Sales manager considers 3 scoring to these 4 data factors on its importance while it is not in the category as 3 most importance sales data in sales staff's aspects.

Interesting issues in big VS small sales data

Big Data: Big data is often said to be characterized by 3Vs: the volume of data, the variety of types of data and the velocity at which it is processed, all of which combine to make big data very difficult to manage (Ahmed, 2016). Its datasets are really huge and complex that conventional data processing techniques cannot manage them are known as big data.

Small Data: It can be defined as small datasets that are capable of impacting decisions in the present. Anything that is currently ongoing and whose data can be accumulated in an Excel file. Small Data is also helpful in making decisions, but is not intended to have a large impact on business, rather for a short period of time. In nutshell, data that is simple enough to be used for human understanding in such a volume and structure that makes it accessible, concise, and workable is known as small data (Rituraj, 2021). Small data is data in a volume and format that makes it accessible, informative and actionable

Small data or traditional data processing has transformed because how data is generated today has transformed (Davenport, 2013). Historically business was about transactions – orders, sales, shipments, inventory, and accounting, to list a few examples. Transactional data is structured, stable, and understood by organizations. Structured data is formatted in rows and columns. Transactional data is primarily used for decision support. The differentiating points between transactional data and Big Data are volume, variety, and velocity (3 V's). Volume refers to the amount of data, variety is based on the types of data sources, and the velocity represents the age of data. Transactional data is structured, well understood, and volume is tens of terabytes or less Volume for Big Data is measured in excess of 100 terabytes or petabytes (although research in this threshold varies). Big Data is characterized by data types considered unstructured – not predefined or known – thus a high degree of variety. Velocity of Big Data can be measured in less than a few minutes. Big Data is used in machine learning and predictive analysis where organizations focus on “what will happen” versus “what has happened” (Larson & Chang, 2016). Organizations of all types are developing data-based offerings to remain competitive.

Ethical issues in data access, in the digital world, data breaches (both the personal data and materials data) are common. customer privacy and data security are concerns of today's consumers (DalleMule& Davenport,

2017). There are many unethical business phenomena revealed by media in the past, such as customer are forced to fill in personal information to install an application or to buy a product or service, open some unnecessary authority (e.g., location, contact list, picture) to these applications. It is not new for us to hear that customer's personal data was sold to other third party. Some e-commerce platforms take advantage of big data for differentiated pricing. Because of the datafication of the business models there needs to be an emphasis on trusted data. Only trustworthy data are useful, the insufficient (missing, wrong, distorted) or messy data (incomplete data) is damaging to business as they are severely restricting the quality of decision making (Jesse, 2021).

Conclusion

With the rapid development of internet, computer, cloud storage, data analysis technologies, there are more and more data available in the world and probably one of the sources to offer these data. How to use these sales data to help business make better decision and make sure all the data's security is still a top topic which need continuously exploration from customer, organizations and government aspects. A successful sales leader need to first understand main sales data to track and goal of analyzing these data.

As competence in sales data is a precondition for a company's decision-making process to lead successfully to profitability. This paper focused on identify critical sales data from the view of salespeople who are currently working in a furniture company in Bangkok, capital of Thailand. Beside this, importance of sales data, its analysis tools and application in practice is also involved in this context.

For furniture products practice in Bangkok, sales target, product performance and sales revenue were identified as the three most essential sales data in the eyes of sales staff with average importance score of 4.91, 4.82 and 4.82 (full score = 5) respectively. These three sales data received four-star rating score as importance data in the sales manager's perspective as well. However, the sales manager believes that the most significant sales data should be given the highest attention is sales growth, with a complete full importance score of 5 points.

Some interesting issues in sales data such as big data, small data and ethical issues are also discussed in the paper. How data were generated today makes sales data transformed to be big data and small data. Both big data and small data can use for analysis. However, there are some differences between these 2 types of data. Big data characterized by 3V's (volume, variety, and velocity) and small data or traditional data focus on transaction and characterized by accessible, informative and actionable. Big data brings us convenience to analyze big amount of data quickly, but it also raises some problems. Issues such as data security, data breach, personal privacy and consumer protection was paid more and more attention by the market participants. A better mechanism needs to be established based on fully communication and collaboration among consumers, furniture industry and governments.

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